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Market Capitalization as Percentage of GDP Worldwide

It grew by an average of 37% between 2013 and 2020 for the countries analyzed

The World Bank calculates the value of market capitalization as a percentage of GDP. Market capitalization (also known as market value) is the share price multiplied by the number of shares outstanding (including their different classes) for domestic listed companies. Investment funds, mutual funds and companies whose sole business objective is to hold shares in other listed companies are excluded. The data are year-end values. Data are analyzed in the period 2013-2020. Countries without a complete time series have been omitted.

Ranking of countries by value of market capitalization as % of GDP in 2020. Hong Kong ranks first by value of market capitalization as % of GDP in 2020 with a value of 1777.23%, followed by Iran with a value of 508.22%, followed by Saudi Arabia with the amount of 330.82%, South Africa with the amount of 311.45%, followed by Switzerland with the amount of 270.52%. In the middle of the table are Morocco with an amount of 54.04%, followed by Mauritius with a value of 54.03%, followed by Vietnam with an amount of 53.66%, Indonesia with 46.84% and Russia with 46.53%. The Ivory Coast closes the ranking with an amount of 11.64%, followed by Egypt with an amount of 10.77%, Romania with an amount of 10.15%, Bermuda with an amount of 3.20 %, and from Costa Rica with an amount of 3.5%.

Ranking of countries by value of percentage change in market capitalization in % of GDP between 2013 and 2020. Iran ranks first in value of market capitalization in % of GDP between 2013 and 2020 with an amount of 624.28%, followed by Saudi Arabia with 433.61%, Jamaica with an amount of 261.89%, Vietnam with 154.14%, Kazakhstan with an amount of 138.38%. In the middle of the table are Germany with an amount of 13.25%, followed by Austria with a value of 10.95%, Peru with 7.14%, Slovenia with 6.84%, Croatia with an amount by 6.59%. The ranking is closed by Jordan with -44.13%, Oman with .46.89%, Egypt with -49.58%, Ivory Coast with -57.89%, Bermuda with -85, 9%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient without outliers. Below is a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient adjusted for outliers. The elimination of the outliers is necessary as the data highlight excessively high values for Hong Kong with a growth equal to an amount of +1777.23%. Two clusters are therefore identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: West Bank and Gaza, Turkey, Panama, Tunisia, Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Greece, Austria, Ivory Coast, Hungary, Egypt, Kazakhstan, Slovenia, Poland, Cyprus, Bermuda, Bangladesh, Romania, Mexico, Nigeria , Croatia, Malta, Vietnam, Costa Rica, Russia, Oman,

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Colombia, Peru, New Zealand, Brazil, Indonesia, Morocco, Germany, Iran, United Arab Emirates, Jamaica;

- Cluster 2: South Korea, Australia, Chile, Thailand, Qatar, Japan, India, Philippines, Luxembourg, Canada, Malaysia, Barbados, Mauritius, Spain, Israel, Jordan, China.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that the value of the median of cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 83.16, while the value of Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 28.30%. From a geographical point of view, it appears that Asian countries tend to have higher values than Western ones. The only western countries that are part of cluster 3 are Luxembourg, Spain, Israel and Canada. In cluster 1-C1 there are instead many European, African and Latin American countries. As a result, Asian economies tend to have a higher market capitalization value than Western, African and Latin American countries. There are obviously exceptions such as Luxembourg, Israel, Canada, Australia, and Spain, which despite being countries of the "Western bloc" have high levels of market capitalization relative to GDP. However, it must be considered that an analysis was carried out through the elimination of outliers, among which Hong Kong and the USA certainly stand out. The reasons that can explain the growth in the value of the market capitalization of Asian economies can be traced back to the typical condition of those economies. In fact, Asian countries have higher GDP growth rates than European and Western economies. Therefore, they attract more investment and more financial resources. Capital flows more to Asian countries to seize investment opportunities with the expected high growth rates. Of course, it must be considered that the growth of market capitalization as a percentage of GDP also represents a risk for those economies. In fact, excess credit towards finance is one of the typical methodologies for triggering systemic financial crises. It therefore follows that, on the one hand, the Asian financial markets are growing in financial terms to support the growth of the real economy. On the other hand, however, systemic risks are growing in terms of financial fragility and volatility.

Conclusions. Market capitalization grew significantly between 2013 and 2020 in the countries considered. The growth in market capitalization occurred mainly in Asian countries. In fact, Asian countries have offered more investment opportunities and have attracted more financial resources. In Western countries, apart from the USA, Israel, Canada, Australia, Luxembourg and Spain have also increased their level of market capitalization as a percentage of GDP. Obviously, the growth in the value of market capitalization as a percentage of GDP tends to be positive also associated with the growth of financial risks which could increase the risk of financial crises, volatility and contagion. It therefore follows that it would be necessary to increase controls at an international level to prevent certain errors of economic policy or crises in the sector, such as for example in the real estate sector, from later manifesting themselves as economic crises capable of reducing both the rate of economic growth of Asian countries, and to reduce market capitalization.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Country Name	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
<i>Australia</i>	86,65	87,81	87,89	105,13	113,72	88,41	106,85	129,66
<i>Austria</i>	27,35	21,87	25,15	30,56	36,10	25,67	29,94	30,35
<i>Bangladesh</i>	34,11	39,60	33,57	26,55	29,34	24,08	18,34	24,01
<i>Barbados</i>	85,21	57,14	62,42	64,07	67,27	69,48	63,82	59,52
<i>Bermuda</i>	22,69	24,97	27,80	36,55	38,07	33,12	39,94	3,20
<i>Brazil</i>	41,27	34,36	27,22	42,24	46,27	47,83	63,38	66,96
<i>Canada</i>	114,47	116,04	102,37	130,47	143,52	112,32	138,16	160,32
<i>Chile</i>	95,64	89,92	78,50	85,23	106,63	84,88	73,18	72,63
<i>China</i>	41,26	57,32	74,02	65,17	70,76	45,52	59,63	83,16
<i>Colombia</i>	53,05	38,49	29,29	36,72	38,95	31,07	40,88	39,35
<i>Costa Rica</i>	3,83	4,90	4,17	4,96	4,98	3,85	3,44	3,05
<i>Cote d'Ivoire</i>	27,64	23,98	27,27	25,54	23,78	14,44	13,52	11,64
<i>Croatia</i>	36,19	33,84	36,29	38,52	40,70	33,44	36,62	38,58
<i>Cyprus</i>	8,78	17,36	13,52	11,93	12,30	12,94	16,52	18,77
<i>Egypt, Arab Rep.</i>	21,37	22,93	16,76	10,02	18,74	16,00	13,87	10,77
<i>Germany</i>	51,85	44,70	51,10	49,46	61,29	44,16	53,96	58,72
<i>Greece</i>	34,57	23,42	21,50	19,24	25,32	18,10	26,14	26,99
<i>Hong Kong SAR, China</i>	1124,71	1109,25	1029,42	995,21	1274,79	1055,82	1349,37	1777,23

<i>Hungary</i>	14,59	10,29	14,13	17,54	22,05	18,02	20,05	17,79
<i>India</i>	68,13	82,72	82,96	76,10	96,40	84,44	80,65	97,15
<i>Indonesia</i>	37,99	47,39	41,04	45,69	51,27	46,70	46,76	46,84
<i>Iran, Islamic Rep.</i>	70,17	25,34	21,91	22,06	21,85	43,78	113,05	508,22
<i>Israel</i>	68,28	63,79	80,39	66,43	64,49	49,77	58,98	63,41
<i>Jamaica</i>	23,41	21,13	41,58	45,95	63,51	76,65	99,60	84,71
<i>Japan</i>	87,16	89,40	110,12	99,03	126,20	105,08	120,97	133,07
<i>Jordan</i>	74,78	69,35	65,96	61,60	57,61	52,43	47,27	41,78
<i>Kazakhstan</i>	11,08	10,38	18,92	29,26	27,31	20,63	24,76	26,42
<i>Korea, Rep.</i>	90,06	81,70	84,00	83,63	109,11	81,96	89,91	132,35
<i>Lebanon</i>	22,76	23,55	22,79	23,70	21,67	17,62	14,99	21,14
<i>Luxembourg</i>	120,61	91,81	78,46	97,90	104,45	69,69	63,35	69,69
<i>Malaysia</i>	154,79	135,77	127,08	119,43	142,83	110,93	110,62	129,41
<i>Malta</i>	40,27	31,32	39,72	37,99	38,34	33,04	33,47	33,77
<i>Mauritius</i>	72,74	66,93	60,28	60,09	71,05	66,83	59,68	54,03
<i>Mexico</i>	41,27	36,51	34,33	32,53	35,98	31,50	32,59	36,64
<i>Morocco</i>	46,51	44,28	41,60	51,61	56,56	47,97	50,74	54,04
<i>New Zealand</i>	34,55	36,97	41,75	42,39	45,84	40,65	50,63	62,19
<i>Nigeria</i>	15,50	10,93	10,14	7,36	9,91	7,47	9,26	13,09
<i>Oman</i>	40,88	40,81	52,25	30,99	26,34	20,53	19,44	21,71
<i>Panama</i>	27,57	27,56	24,36	23,42	24,15	23,25	24,78	24,42
<i>Peru</i>	40,25	39,27	29,80	42,26	47,02	41,95	43,34	43,13
<i>Philippines</i>	76,55	88,02	77,93	75,24	88,41	74,43	73,06	75,41
<i>Poland</i>	39,66	31,33	28,88	29,51	38,39	27,26	25,44	29,61
<i>Qatar</i>	76,78	90,13	88,14	102,04	81,07	88,93	90,75	114,53
<i>Romania</i>	12,95	11,21	10,42	9,75	11,24	8,57	10,40	10,15
<i>Russian Federation</i>	33,62	18,74	28,84	48,72	39,60	34,76	46,75	46,53
<i>Saudi Arabia</i>	62,00	63,02	62,89	67,39	63,13	58,63	287,02	330,82
<i>Singapore</i>	242,03	239,10	207,78	200,74	229,34	182,36	185,03	187,32
<i>Slovenia</i>	14,72	15,04	14,00	11,76	13,00	13,41	14,58	15,73
<i>South Africa</i>	235,18	245,00	212,27	293,99	322,71	214,11	271,88	311,45
<i>Spain</i>	82,37	72,38	65,81	57,12	67,68	50,90	57,18	59,45
<i>Sri Lanka</i>	24,42	28,68	24,43	21,22	20,09	16,48	17,66	18,93
<i>Switzerland</i>	218,16	205,81	218,89	204,01	242,59	198,63	254,30	270,52
<i>Thailand</i>	84,31	105,67	86,92	104,74	120,26	98,81	104,64	108,53
<i>Tunisia</i>	17,67	17,39	19,26	19,05	21,16	19,51	20,29	20,15
<i>Turkiye</i>	20,44	23,41	21,85	19,75	26,49	19,17	24,34	32,97
<i>United Arab Emirates</i>	45,06	48,68	52,90	57,74	59,44	54,18	59,05	84,36
<i>United States</i>	142,70	150,03	137,69	146,31	164,91	148,23	158,51	193,35
<i>Vietnam</i>	21,12	22,46	24,55	28,48	44,54	42,78	44,81	53,66
<i>West Bank and Gaza</i>	24,03	22,78	23,90	22,01	24,13	22,95	21,93	22,19